

The Pattern of Referrals to Lifestyle Clinics in PHCs, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

Shatha Ali A. AlGhaleb ,
Nasser Abdullah Alaqil, Jalham Jaman O. Alsehali,
Abdullah Ali Abdullah Mashhor, Hanan Ali Abdullah Alghalib,
Mohammed Salem Mohammed Alshehri, Turke Nasser A. Alhawasi,
Mostafa Kofi
Family Medicine Dept., Prince Sultan Military Medical City, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

Abstract

Introduction: lifestyle medicine is the cornerstone of a healthy population for the prevention of disease and promotion of health attitudes and practices among community members. Description of referred population to lifestyle medicine clinic is mandatory for health care planning and allocation of resources. This study aims to describe the pattern of the referred population to the lifestyle clinic in primary health care centers in Riyadh Saudi Arabia.

Methods: cross-sectional study for registry of patients referred to Lifestyle clinic, data collection for January 2023 to October 2023 were collected. Sociodemographic characteristics of the referred patients to the Lifestyle clinic were produced.

Results: during the study duration from January 2023 to October 2023, a total of 1228 patients were referred to the lifestyle clinic, 598 (48.7%) were females and 630 (51.3%) were males. The age of patients referred to the lifestyle clinic ranged from 18 to 74 years, with a mean age of 42.28 years and an SD of 14.8 years old.

Conclusion and recommendations: Lifestyle clinic referrals are from different age groups and from both genders. The lifestyle clinic is receiving a variety of patients from different clinics such general primary health care clinics and family medicine. There is a more detailed larger studies both quantitative and qualitative studies to describe the pattern of patients and their general needs to better planning of health care resources and improvement of health care services.

Introduction

Huge efforts have been compiled for the establishment and continuation of lifestyle clinic services, and it's needed to explain who and which are the referred populations to the clinics. This descriptive study will explain in detail the sociodemographic characteristics of the study population.

We will describe gender frequency and age groups frequently referred from general clinics in PHCs to the lifestyle clinic, this will support health care planning and allocation of resources.

Aim

This study aims to identify the pattern of referred patients to Lifestyle medicine clinic.

Objectives

1. What are genders of referred patients to Lifestyle medicine clinic?
2. What are the age groups of patients referred to the Lifestyle clinic?
3. What are sociodemographic characteristics such as age and gender of referred patients to Life Lifestyle clinic?

Review of literature

A report by the World Health Organization states that over 73% of fatalities worldwide are caused by noncommunicable diseases (NCD). Heart-related conditions are responsible for the bulk of deaths from NCDs each year. Lifestyle variables that greatly increase the chance of dying from NCD include using tobacco

More Information

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Keywords:

lifestyle clinic,
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products, not exercising, maintaining poor eating habits, and using drugs [1].

Nevertheless, there is insufficient attention given to a number of these NCD risk factors. The preventative concept is the most effective and crucial approach to the current state of affairs, since it emphasizes preventing the spread of illnesses [2].

Making healthy lifestyle choices can prevent 80% of death from cardiovascular illnesses and type 2 diabetes. Numerous long-term observational studies and systematic reviews involving a sizable population have demonstrated the consistent and substantial correlation between lifestyle factors and overall mortality, cardiovascular morbidity and mortality, and the prevalence of chronic diseases and disabilities [3-9]. According to the ACLM, lifestyle medicine is the way of the future for managing chronic illnesses. KSA is currently leading the Arab world in this initiative, with numerous scientists, collaborative, and organizational activities. We are participating in many of these events thanks to the identification and participation of our

qualified healthcare team. Our goal is to improve the quality of life and provide benefits to PSMC patients as the foundation for realizing our vision and purpose. Furthermore, we believe that other distributed health care services can be inferred from our experience, which justifies their discussion in order to make better extrapolations in the future.

Referral patterns have significant implications because they represent patient expectations, medical practice areas, and standards of care. It has critical consequences for human resource planning and resource utilization estimates. Referral rates differ based on methods and area, patient characteristics, physician characteristics, and health care policy [10-19].

Methods

Study type: Cross-sectional general survey study for data records.

Target population: patients data referred to lifestyle clinic.

Table 1. Data collection form

Center	DATE-MONTH	DATE-YEAR	SN	PT-NUMB	Gender	Age
RIYADH WAZARAT						
RIYADH WAZARAT						

Study variables: center, date-month-date-year, SN, PT-Number, Gender, Age

Sampling method: comprehensive nonprobability

Sample size: all patients referred to Lifestyle clinic at PHC will be included for the year 2023.

Data management and statistical plan:

Data analysis will be conducted using SPSS statistical software. Descriptive statistics, encompassing measures of central tendency (mean), dispersion (standard deviation), frequency distribution, and percentage composition, will be employed to comprehensively characterize and summarize the quantitative and categorical variables. Bivariate statistical analysis will be utilized to assess the relationships between variables, employing appropriate statistical tests such as chi-square, Student's t-test, one-way analysis of variance, and Pearson's correlation, contingent upon the study design and the outcome variables under investigation. A p-value of less than 0.05 will be considered statistically significant, indicating a 95% confidence level that the observed relationship between the variables is not attributable to chance.

The study proposal was submitted to the PSMC-IRB Committee and an approval letter was issued Proposal ID #641 IRB Approval # E-2299 On 13 March 2024.

Results

From Figure 1 we can see that the Lifestyle clinic was a busy clinic of referrals all over the months of study duration, the least referrals were in June due to summary time and school leaves.

From Figure 2 we notice that both genders had the same interests and referrals to the Lifestyle clinic.

In Table 2 there is a total of 1228 patients were referred to the Lifestyle clinic in about 10 months of study duration with the least referrals in June 59 patients (4.8%) and the biggest is during October when 160 patients were referred to the Lifestyle clinic (13%).

From Table 4 the minimum age of patients referred to the Lifestyle clinic was 18 years old, and the maximum age was 74 years old, and the mean age was 42.28 and SE 0.424.

In Table 5 there is a cross-tabulation for the number of referrals and gender, males in general were referred to the Lifestyle clinic more than females. However, there is no statistically significant difference between gender referrals to the Lifestyle medicine clinic. The gender difference in referrals is graphically represented in Figure 3.

Table 6 a comparison of patients' age means referred to the Lifestyle medicine clinic for the different months of the study duration. Also, the same table presents an ANOVA test for the means differences of age for different months of the study duration. The table

followed by the PLOT for age in different months for study duration. The PLOT of means of ages shows that

the highest mean age was in June and September and the lowest was in the months of July and October.

Figure 1: Bar Chart for Frequency of Referrals by Month to Lifestyle Clinic During 2023

Figure 2: Bar Chart of Gender Referral to Lifestyle Clinic During 2023

Table 2: Frequency and Percentages for Number of Referrals to Lifestyle Clinic in 2023

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	1	151	12.3
	2	159	12.9
	3	101	8.2
	4	105	8.6
	5	150	12.2
	6	59	4.8
	7	105	8.6
	8	133	10.8
	9	105	8.6
	10	160	13.0
	Total	1228	100.0

Table 3: Frequency and Percentages of Gender Referral to Lifestyle Clinic During 2023

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	F	598	48.7
	M	630	51.3
	Total	1228	100.0

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics for Age of Referrals to Lifestyle Clinic 2023

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error
Age	1228	56	18	74	51914	42.28	.424
Valid N (listwise)	1228						

Table 5. Crosstabulation for Referral Gender and Months 2023

			Gender		Total
			F	M	
MonthYear	1 January	Count	73	78	151
		% within MonthYear	48.3%	51.7%	100.0%
	2 February	Count	80	79	159
		% within MonthYear	50.3%	49.7%	100.0%
	3 March	Count	48	53	101
		% within MonthYear	47.5%	52.5%	100.0%
	4 April	Count	52	53	105
		% within MonthYear	49.5%	50.5%	100.0%
	5 May	Count	70	80	150
		% within MonthYear	46.7%	53.3%	100.0%
	6 June	Count	25	34	59
		% within MonthYear	42.4%	57.6%	100.0%
	7 July	Count	51	54	105
		% within MonthYear	48.6%	51.4%	100.0%
	8 August	Count	64	69	133
		% within MonthYear	48.1%	51.9%	100.0%
	9 September	Count	54	51	105
		% within MonthYear	51.4%	48.6%	100.0%
	10 October	Count	81	79	160
		% within MonthYear	50.6%	49.4%	100.0%
Total		Count	598	630	1228
		% within MonthYear	48.7%	51.3%	100.0%

Table 6: Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.020 ^a	9	.991
Likelihood Ratio	2.025	9	.991
N of Valid Cases	1228		

Note: a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 28.73.

Figure 3: Bar Chart for Referral to Lifestyle Clinic Gender per Each Month 2023

Table 7: Comparison of Age of Referral to Lifestyle Clinic per Month in 2023

Descriptives					
Age					
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean
					Lower Bound
1	151	42.07	14.711	1.197	39.71
2	159	43.26	14.871	1.179	40.93
3	101	41.55	14.493	1.442	38.69
4	105	42.37	15.343	1.497	39.40
5	150	43.04	14.940	1.220	40.63
6	59	43.81	15.149	1.972	39.87
7	105	38.61	15.036	1.467	35.70
8	133	42.96	15.178	1.316	40.36
9	105	45.78	14.941	1.458	42.89
10	160	40.13	13.828	1.093	37.97
Total	1228	42.28	14.860	.424	41.44
Model	Fixed Effects		14.806	.423	41.45
	Random Effects			.608	40.90

Table 8: Test of Homogeneity of Variances

		Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Age	Based on Mean	.460	9	1218	.901
	Based on Median	.381	9	1218	.944
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	.381	9	1187.899	.944
	Based on trimmed mean	.434	9	1218	.917

Table 9: ANOVA

Age						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	
Between Groups	(Combined)	3940.159	9	437.795	1.997	
	Linear Term	Unweighted	4.408	1	4.408	.020
		Weighted	64.060	1	64.060	.292
		Deviation	3876.099	8	484.512	2.210
Within Groups		267000.808	1218	219.212		
Total		270940.967	1227			

Figure 4: Means Plots of Age of Referrals for Lifestyle Clinic in 2023

Discussion

Referrals to lifestyle clinics are from different specialty clinics, but mainly from primary health care clinics, with almost equal proportions in both genders, many referrals are distributed all over the months of the study, but much less in June and July, and maximum at February and October.

"The evidence-based practice of helping individuals and families adopt and sustain healthy behaviors that affect health and quality of life" is the definition of lifestyle medicine (LSM) [20-21].

Its six foundations are as follows: a diet high in healthy foods and plants, consistent exercise, restorative sleep, stress management, abstinence from dangerous substances, and wholesome social interactions. Both the treatment and reversal of chronic diseases depend on these pillars. Additionally, they have a significant influence on prevention [22]. In a study by Monica Peek et al., a larger study included Characteristics of Patient Visits, (N=6852) and age and gender, which had a similar finding of the same distribution for gender and age groups and means comparable to our findings [23]. Having a description of patients referred to the lifestyle medicine clinic helps decision-makers and health care services planners to allocate resources and plan for improvement of the health care services provided. Also, helps in planning for interventions for improvements of lifestyle by introducing specific health education activities and plans for any motivational interviews during consultations at the lifestyle clinic.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The lifestyle clinic is receiving a variety of patients from different age groups and gender referred from different clinics such general primary health care clinics and family medicine. There is a more detailed larger studies both quantitative and qualitative studies to describe the pattern of patients and their general needs in order to better planning of health care resources and improvement of health care services.

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